

Value addition to temple waste – A study

Raji S.*^a, D. D. Sarode^a, Suhel Gholap^b and Swapnil Gangrude^b

^aDepartment of General Engineering, Institute of Chemical Technology, Matunga,
Mumbai-400 019, India

E-mail : dd.sarode@ictmumbai.edu.in, ge14s.raji@pg.ictmumbai.edu.in

^bSSJCET, Asangaon, Shahapur Tal, Thane-421 601, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : suhel800@gmail.com, gangrudeswapnil5@gmail.com

Manuscript received 15 November 2017, revised 26 February 2018, accepted 07 March 2018

Abstract : The increase in waste generation and the cost of collection, transportation and disposal are the major concern in developing countries. In urban cities the flower waste generated in temples is presently piled at one place or disposed of in nearby water bodies or dumped on land to decay which causes several environmental problems such as water pollution and other health hazards. Temple waste consists of organic waste like flowers, leaves, coconut shells, coconut fiber, pith, waste oil, pieces of cotton wicks, residues or ash of burned incense sticks, etc. which find their way ultimately into bins or some water bodies and thereby resulting pollution. Degradation of floral waste is a very slow process as compared to kitchen waste degradation. Therefore, there is a need for proper and environment friendly process of disposal of floral waste. The present study has reviewed various methods reported for the utilization of temple waste. There is a vast scope of using the floral and other wastes as a potential fuel or a replacement material such as wood in the burning process or in Homa Haven. This will have benefits of solving the disposal problem and can minimize the use of existing precious source of fuel i.e. wood.

Keywords : Temple waste, briquettes, floral waste.

I. Introduction

Flowers come as waste from various sources like, marriage halls, temples, Dargah and various other cultural and religious ceremonies¹. In India, religion is a path of life and it is an intrinsic element of the entire Indian culture to offer to God. People worship God and are accustomed to go to the temples offering flowers, fruits, coconuts and sweets, etc. The bulk of the flowers, leaves of different plants, coconut shells, milk and curd are piled up and then disposed off exclusively in water bodies¹. Everyday these flowers are offered by devotees in temples, are left after pooja and therefore become waste. In India festivals are celebrated throughout the year that eventually lead to generation of solid waste. This proportion of waste is generally neglected and requires due consideration¹. Thus, the aim of the present paper is

to review various options reported for the utilization of temple waste. A study has been conducted on disposal of temple waste at Kashi Vishwanath temple in Varanasi. Temple has its own system for disposal of large quantity of waste resulting from offerings by devotees; the floral waste generated in the temple is converted into manure². To avoid ill effects caused by disposal of these offerings, they can be reused to make some valuable products from these wastes. Burning of incense sticks produces smoke (fumes) which contains Particulate Matter (PM), gaseous products and many organic compounds, therefore flower petals obtained from temples can be used to make herbal incense sticks. Flowers like Genda (Marigold) are used to make incense sticks, while roses are converted to rose water¹. Besides incense sticks and rose water, the flowers can also be incorporated

into herbal products such as herbal colors, natural dyes etc.³. Another case where floral waste management has yielded good result is that of Ajmer Sharif Dargah of Khwaja Moinuddin Chishti where nearly 1.5 to 1.8 tonnes of flowers, offered each day were used to be dumped in a well⁴. With technical assistance from Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plant (CIMAP), Lucknow, the Dargah Committee has established a rose water distillation plant at the outskirts of Ajmer. Study reveals that safe methodology of converting to biogas will help in generating alternate source of energy. Singh and Bajpai¹⁰ worked on anaerobic digestion of flower waste for biogas production. Biogas produced can be used as fuel to prepare food. Shouche *et al.*⁹ used various processes like composting followed by vermicomposting to manage floral waste. They used different proportion of mixtures of cattle dung and floral wastes to prepare vermin compost. By converting the waste, flowers are not only recycled, but also generate employment and revenue for local women.

Many of the above mentioned processes are not cost-effective and hence are not suitable in urban cities due to scarcity of land⁵. Composting is time-consuming process and takes a lot of time to decompose so it is not broadly adopted¹¹. It has its own demerits, as it requires large area. It cannot be used in cities. Digging pits are very frequently required and manure produced from it was not much worth as compared to time taken. Method replacing composting is Vermi composting. It is as same as Composting but in this technique worms are used as they eat organic waste and there excreta is very rich in urea. Bio-gas plant can be set in village level where ample of space is available. Small temples can operate these plants on their own. It may be little inflexible to use these technique in cities due to lack of free space, but a truck carrying this throw away to remote area from urban area can be feasibly used. These techniques can be used for business purposes and also are eco-friendly techniques⁶.

There are many methods presently available for treating the flora waste, many of them are uneconomical and many of them require large area for processing. One of the approaches for efficient utilization of all biomass waste is its densification by converting it in the form of pellets or biomass briquettes. The present study is focused on this technique. Briquette is made by compressing floral waste along with other waste generated from temples and which is further used as fuel.

II. Materials and methods

For carrying out this study, the area chosen is a small city. The information about quantity of flower waste, ash and other waste generated from 71 temples. Small and medium size temples, based on waste generated, has been collected. About 100 kg of flower waste, 0.200 kg/temple/day of ash and 0.125 kg/temple/day is generated daily from various temples and the present disposal method adopted is open dumping or in bins provided by Municipal Corporation or disposed in water bodies in case of less quantity. During holidays and festival days amount of waste generated is about 150 to 250 kg per day.

A. Processing of flower waste

After collection of flower waste from temples thread and other decorative items were removed by hand sorting and garlands and flowers were segregated and shredded into small pieces. Ash obtained from burning of incense sticks have been used as a binder. Waste oil and coconut dust were collected and added to flower waste in proportions and made briquettes by compressing it in a cylindrical mould.

B. Analytical method

Characteristics of flower waste biomass such as moisture content, ash content, volatile matter and fixed carbon were determined by standard procedures (IS 1350 (Part 1) : 1984). The moisture content of the samples was determined by the loss in weight when dried in a laboratory oven at 105°C for 1 h. The volatile matter has been determined by keeping

the oven dried sample of about 1 g in a muffle furnace at 950°C for 6 min. To determine the ash content, the samples were heated in a laboratory ash furnace at 750°C for 3 h. Fixed carbon was determined by subtracting moisture content, volatile matter and ash content from 100. The results of the proximate analyses of flower waste, being the major constituent, were shown in Table 2.

A dried flower waste sample was weighed and placed in a digital Bomb calorimeter for determination of calorific value. The digital Bomb calorimeter then sealed and the biomass sample was ignited electrically (IS 1350 (Part 2)). The complete combustion of the biomass releases heat and it was measured through the temperature change, using a digital sensor, of the water bath surrounding the bomb calorimeter. The result has been reported in Table 2.

C. Experimental setup

Flower waste, ash from incense sticks, cotton wicks, coconut waste are collected from temples. Flowers are sun dried for 1 to 5 days. Samples were crushed into small pieces of 2 to 3 mm size. Crushed sample with other waste such as oil, incense stick ash or water in different combination. Four sets of sample of briquettes were made. Samples 1 with 100% flower waste, Sample 2 with 85% flower waste and 15% oil, Sample 3 with 90% flower waste and 10% coconut dust and Sample 4 with 95% flower waste and 5% ash. Then the sample mix was fed into a cylindrical mould and filled it in layers by tamping with a rod. After compressing for 30 min, briquette was dried in sunlight.

III. Results and discussion

The moisture content of flower samples as received from the temples were found to range from 28 to 31%. For determination of density, three briquettes from each batch were tested. Respective heights and diameters at two different points using digital calipers were measured. From the data obtained, the density after drying (relaxed density) was

computed as the ratio of the measured mass to the calculated volume. Average density was 235 kg/m³.

Table 1. Physical characteristics of briquette

Parameters	Value
Diameter (mm)	62
Length (mm)	30
Bulk density (kg/m ³)	235
Moisture content (%)	8

Table 2. Proximate analysis of flower waste

Parameters	Value
Moisture content (%)	9.235
Ash content (%)	6.11
Volatile matter (%)	69.12
Fixed carbon (%)	15.535
Gross calorific value (kcal/100 g)	Value
Flower waste	206.52
Flower waste + oil	630.48
Flower waste + coconut dust	598.49
Flower waste + ash	370.28

Based on the result obtained, waste oil mixed with flower waste had a gross calorific value of 630.48 kcal/100 g, shown better result as compared to only flower waste. Flower mixed with incense stick ash had shown reasonably high calorific value of 370.28 kcal/100 g. The density of briquette was 235 kg/m³. However, the value is less than the density of the wood chips. Through briquetting process the density of the waste materials has been increased which improves the handling characteristics.

IV. Conclusion

In this paper characterization of temple waste has been done by estimating Proximate Analysis and heating value of pellets. Based on the result obtained flower waste pellets have shown less calorific value. Pellets obtained by combination of waste generated from temples have good calorific value and can be used as fuel. Waste oil mixed with flowers had shown better result as compared to water with flowers. Flower waste mixed with incense stick ash had shown reasonably high calorific value as compared to flower

with water. This method can be used in temples for the preparation of food offerings, thereby preventing water pollution and reducing the amount of flower waste going to land fill.

References

1. A. Boraste, K. K. Vamsi, A. Jhadav, Y. Khairnar, N. Gupta, S. Trivedi, P. Patil, G. Gupta, M. Gupta, A. K. Mujapara and B. Joshi, *International Journal of Microbiology Research*, 2009, **1(2)**, 23.
2. Chickballapur Market towards Development of Value Added Products (Project Reference No. 37s1018, Biotechnology).
3. M. V. Gaurav and G. R. Pathade, *Universal Journal of Environment and Research Technology*, 2011, **1(2)**, 182.
4. M. A. Khan and S. U. Rehman, *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 2005, **7(6)**, 973.
5. M. S. Kumar and K. Swapanavahini, *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science and Technology*, 2012, **1(2)**, 125.
6. M. Makhani and A. Upadhyay, *International Journal of Innovative and Emerging Research in Engineering*, 2015, **2(1)**, 145.
7. J. L. Navarrete-Bolaños, O. Serrato-Joya, E. Botello-Alvarez, H. Jimenez-Islas, M. Cardenas Manriquez, E. Conde-Barajas and R. Rico Martínez, "Analyzing microbial consortia for biotechnological processes design. Communicating Current Research and Educational Topics and Trends in Applied Microbiology", ed. A. Méndez-Vilas, 2007, pp. 437-449.
8. K. Perumal, T. A. Moorthy and J. S. Savitha, *Asian Journal of Experimental Biology and Science*, 2012, **3(2)**, 330.
9. S. Shouche, A. Pandey and P. Bhati, *Journal of Environment and Research*, 2011, **6(1)**, 63.
10. P. Singh and U. Bajpai, *Environmental Progress and Sustainable Energy*, 2012, **31(4)**, 637.
11. S. K. Singh and R. S. Singh, *Indian Journal of Environmental Protection*, 2007, **18(11)**, 850.
12. H. Siti Zulaiha, M. A. Hassan, I. S. A. Sheikh, M. S. Siti Hajar, S. Mohamad Roji and A. Ramlan, *Malaysian Journal of Microbiology*, 2013, **9(1)**, 60.
13. Tanaya Singh, (2016) Entrepreneurs, Environment, 1972. ActaHortic. 26, 374.
14. H. L. S. Tandon, "Methods of analysis of soils, plants, Waters and fertilizers", Fertilizer Development and Consultation Organization, ed. H. L. S. Tandon, New delhi, India, 1993, pp. 36-48.
15. P. Tiwari, "Utilization and Management of Floral Waste Generated in Popular Temples of Jaipur City", The IIS University, Jaipur, 2014.
16. "A novel approach in utilization of flower waste from Chickballapur market towards development of value added products", Project Reference No. 37S1018.
17. S. Agarwal, "Report on demonstration of renewable energy system at Shri Mahakaleshwar Temple Complex in Ujjain", Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, New Delhi, 2011, 1-4. [4] C.-H.